

EXPRESSION OF NATIONAL CUSTOMS AND TRADITIONS IN PAREMIA AND PHRASEOLOGISMS

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the paremiological and fraseological units related to food culture in English and Uzbek, and describes the concept and importance of national food culture in its development with extensive examples.

Introduction. The national customs and traditions of each people are expressed through their language and examples of oral creativity. Folk proverbs, sayings and various phraseological units serve as a “mirror” of these national values. As W. Mieder noted, proverbs embody the experience, lifestyle and worldview of the people accumulated over the centuries, therefore it is not for nothing that they are called “*the treasury of folk wisdom*”. Indeed, proverbs, as a product of national consciousness, reflect the culture and spirit of a people. Similarly, phraseologisms - stable expressions and sayings that have arisen in the language of the people - also express the national character, lifestyle and even historical traditions, if not literally, then figuratively and figuratively. Proverbs and idioms are not only stylistic means in the language, but also serve as national and cultural symbols. Through them, the historical experience, spiritual values, and worldview of the people are passed down from generation to generation. A number of criteria and principles are followed in the comparative study of paremia (proverbs, sayings, wise sayings) and phraseologisms of the English and Uzbek peoples. The main directions of such study are presented below:

Thematic analysis: It is necessary to classify the topics that proverbs and idioms are about. In particular, proverbs and idioms on topics such as family traditions, hospitality, attitude to work and profession, moral standards, nature and the animal world, etc. are grouped separately. This method shows which topics are mentioned most often in each national language and which values are emphasized. **Semantic-comparative analysis:** The principle of comparing the content and essence of proverbs and phraseologisms is used. This method compares the direct meaning of the expressions in two languages and the conclusion or advice given through them. It is determined to what extent the universal content is in proverbs and idioms, and in what ways national identity is manifested. As researchers have noted, proverbs of different peoples contain common wisdom, that is, universality, arising from similar life situations, and this is observed even in proverbs of historically and ethnically distant peoples. For example, in English and Uzbek there is a proverb with the meaning “*Yetti o'lchab, bir kes*”: in English this idea is

expressed in the form *"Measure twice, cut once"*, while in Uzbek it is said *"Yetti marta o'lchab, bir marta kes"* - both of which teach that one should act without haste and think carefully.

The words, images and symbols contained in phraseologisms are analyzed. Because in each language, stable expressions can refer to the national realities of that people - in particular, traditional items, dishes, animals or historical figures. For example, the English idiom *"to carry coals to Newcastle"* is associated with the coal wealth of the city of Newcastle and means *"to do something unnecessary"*. In Uzbek, there is also an expression *"Qumga suv quymoq"* (to pour water on the sand) to express an unnecessary, meaningless action, which is expressed in an image suitable for local conditions. Therefore, the same meaning can be conveyed in two languages differently, through scenes close to the life of that people.

The principle of determining the degree of equivalence determines whether a proverb or phraseologism in one language has a direct equivalent in another language. Some proverbs are found in both nations with almost the same content and form (*"Better late than never"* - *"Better late than never"*), some are similar in content but differ in imagery and expression (*"Every dog has his day"* - *"When luck comes, the mouse defeats the elephant"*, i.e. when luck comes, the weak defeat the strong), and some are unique to that nation and have no direct equivalent in other languages and cultures. For example, while the Uzbek proverb *"Mehmon otangdan ulug'"* (*a guest is respected as highly as his father*) is widespread, there is no direct proverb with this content in English. In English, there is a proverb about a guest with the opposite meaning, *"Fish and guests smell after three days,"* which clearly shows the difference in the mentality of the two peoples.

When studying proverbs and idioms, attention is also paid to the problem of translating them into another language. After all, translating stable expressions literally often loses their *"spirit"*. Therefore, the method of finding an equivalent proverb or explaining it is used in translation. The main principle in the translation of proverbs is to preserve the figurative meaning. For example, although the English proverb *"Let sleeping dogs lie"* is translated into Uzbek as *"Do not press the tail of a sleeping dog"*, sometimes this meaning is expressed in the usual way with the image of a snake in the form *"Do not follow a sleeping snake"*. In both cases, the meaning - not to disturb the peace - is preserved, but the images are different (dog in English, snake in Uzbek).

Conclusion. So, an important principle in translation is to preserve the meaning, and if necessary, replace the image with a suitable national symbol. The analysis based on the above criteria and principles is in the linguo-cultural direction, which allows us to study the culture and thinking of the people through language. In particular, G. Permyakov noted that proverbs in different languages have common patterns, and the generalized expression of life situations is consistent among many peoples. At the same time, the unique historical and cultural experience of each people is clearly manifested in some proverbs and expressions, determining their national color. Therefore, in the comparative study of English and Uzbek paremiology, it is necessary to take into account both commonality and national characteristics.

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